

CoMiCProN Meeting May 5th 2026

Minutes

Minute 1. Call to order

Markus Göker called the meeting to order at 17:00 CEST.

Minute 2. Record of attendance

Those **present** were: Rafael Cantón, Markus Göker, Marko Kostovski, Gabriele Margos, Edward R.B. Moore, Henrik Christensen, Volker Fingerle, Udo Reischl and Audrey Schuetz. **Apologies** were received from Susan Butler-Wu, Karen Carroll, Valerie Collin, Sarah Copsey-Mawer, Scott Nguyen, Stefan Emler, Joachim Spergser and José Vázquez-Boland. Some members joined later or had to leave earlier.

Minute 3. Minutes of 2026-04-07 meeting

The April meeting minutes were reviewed and approved without modification.

Minute 4. Matters Arising / Action Points from 2026-04-07 meeting

The action items from the April meeting were reviewed. Some could be marked as either completed or obsolete. Others need to be marked as ongoing. These ongoing items are listed below under “Matters Arising/Action Points” from this meeting.

4.1 All committee members to continue updating and augmenting the CoMiCProN list of potential multipliers (start: 2025-08-05).

The list of potential multipliers is available online and remains open for updates; M. Göker reviewed it under matters arising/action points and noted that he was not sure whether anyone else had added new entries. M. Göker said he had identified one contact person at EMBL/ENA, and that J. Vázquez-Boland had also indicated he was in contact with EMBL/ENA. M. Göker planned to share his contact with J. Vázquez-Boland and discuss what to do next. This action point therefore remains ongoing, and all committee members are reminded to continue updating and augmenting the list as appropriate.

4.2 All committee members to confirm their attendance at the June ASM meeting in Washington, D.C., and coordinate logistics with E.R.B. Moore (start: 2026-01-13).

M. Göker asked whether anyone else had contacted E.R.B. Moore regarding attendance at the ASM meeting, and it was noted that only S. Nguyen and J. Vázquez-Boland had indicated they would attend, with no further coordination updates provided.

4.3 All committee members to assess and contribute, where possible, to the IJSEM manuscript on the return of the subgenus, to be revisited at a future meeting (start: 2026-02-10).

No substantial update was provided regarding the manuscript on the return of the subgenus, as the item was considered not very urgent and no further progress was reported during the meeting.

4.4 S. Butler-Wu to continue efforts to identify the appropriate contact person for risk group classification in the USA (start: 2024-04-02).

As S. Butler-Wu was absent from the meeting, no update was provided regarding efforts to identify the appropriate contact person for risk group classification in the USA.

4.5 V. Collin to liaise with M. Göker regarding the usage of LoRN by bioMérieux (start: 2025-09-02).

As V. Collin sent apologies and was absent from the meeting, no update was provided regarding liaison with M. Göker on the usage of LoRN by bioMérieux.

4.6 S. Copsey-Mawer to follow up with NCTC contacts regarding potential CoMiCProN membership candidates (start: 2025-12-02).

As S. Copsey-Mawer was absent from the meeting, no update was provided regarding follow-up with NCTC contacts on potential CoMiCProN membership candidates.

4.7 CoMiCProN members (including but not limited to V. Fingerle) to finalize preparation of the ESCMID presentation and ensure submission by 15 April (start: 2026-03-10).

The committee noted that preparation of the ESCMID presentation had been finalized and successfully submitted by the 15 April deadline. During the later conference report discussion, V. Fingerle explained that the presentation had been prepared collaboratively with important contributions and corrections from several members, particularly M. Göker and E.R.B. Moore, and thanked them for their assistance. V. Fingerle further reported that S. Butler-Wu had attended the conference, that the presentation had generated interest and positive feedback from attendees, and that several participants approached him afterwards to discuss the topic further. Future possibilities for additional ESCMID sessions or educational activities related to bacterial nomenclature and taxonomy were also briefly discussed. This action point was considered completed.

4.8 M. Göker to continue assessing the possible inclusion of plant pathogens in LoRN and report updates (start: 2025-07-15).

M. Göker reported ongoing discussions regarding the possible inclusion of plant pathogens in LoRN, noting that he had been in contact with G. Bull from the plant pathology community and that further discussion on the matter would follow later in the meeting.

4.9 G. Margos to proceed with targeted communication with PubMLST database curators, following further clarification of approach (start: 2026-05-05).

M. Göker reported that the PubMLSTlist provided by G. Margos had been checked for agreement with LoRN and that the curators to contact were noted. G. Margos added that she had questions and regarding the appropriate strategy for approaching the PubMLST database curators, and indicated that she would follow up with M. Göker by email to clarify the proposed communication approach.

4.10 E.R.B. Moore to update the CoMiCProN details on the ICSP website, including the Zenodo link for meeting minutes (start: 2025-12-02).

E.R.B. Moore briefly acknowledged that updating the CoMiCProN details on the ICSP website, including the relevant Zenodo information, remained ongoing, although no detailed progress report was provided during the meeting.

4.11 E.R.B. Moore to prepare and circulate a draft response to NCBI regarding ICSP representation at the workshop (start: 2026-05-05).

E.R.B. Moore reported that he was still preparing a response regarding the lack of ICSP representation at the NCBI workshop during the ASM conference and intended to circulate it for comments, emphasizing that the ICSP should also be recognized as responsible for nomenclature of uncultivated taxa.

4.12 J. Vázquez-Boland to initiate contact with EMBL/ENA to arrange a meeting on prokaryotic nomenclature (start: 2025-10-21).

It was reported that J. Vázquez-Boland had established contact with someone at EMBL/ENA regarding a possible meeting on prokaryotic nomenclature, while M. Göker noted that he would share his own EMBL/ENA contact information with José so they could further coordinate how to proceed.

4.13 J. Vázquez-Boland to follow up on the *Rhodococcus hoagii* issue in the Bruker database with relevant stakeholders (start: 2026-02-10).

As neither J. Vázquez-Boland nor M. Cordovana were present at the meeting, no update was provided regarding discussions on the issue of *Rhodococcus hoagii* in the Bruker database.

4.14 M. Kostovski or M. Göker to upload the minutes of the March meeting to Zenodo (start: 2026-05-05).

Regarding the newly introduced action point on archiving meeting documentation, M. Göker and M. Kostovski reported that the minutes of the March meeting had already been uploaded to Zenodo.

Minute 5. Votes on the new candidates for membership in the committee

Under the agenda item concerning new members and committee membership, the committee noted that there were no specific new attempts to recruit additional members to discuss at this meeting.

Minute 6. Report on inactive members and votes on their removal

In accordance with the committee guidelines regarding inactive membership, the committee discussed the status of N. Moss, who had neither attended meetings nor communicated with the committee since October of the previous year, and subsequently conducted a ballot on her removing from the committee, resulting in 6 votes in favour, 2 against, and 0 abstentions, ultimately deciding to remove her from membership while noting that she would be welcome to reapply in the future.

Minute 7. Ongoing online petition “Economy of change regarding bacterial names in databases”. Reports on attempts to get multipliers to act as such, i.e. reports on when they were asked to send the request to

sign the petition to all their members, what they replied, and what was done in case of a negative response.

The online petition remains active, and an increase in signatures has been observed following its distribution via professional societies.

With regard to dissemination through specific organizations:

- a) Deutsche Gesellschaft für Hygiene und Mikrobiologie (DGHM) – M. Göker reported that the society had successfully distributed the petition among its members, resulting in an immediate and substantial increase in signatures.
- b) Swiss Society for Microbiology (SSM) – S. Emler successfully facilitated dissemination of the petition through the society, which was followed by a noticeable increase in signatures.
- c) Macedonian Microbiology Society (MMS) – however, M. Kostovski noted that the society is relatively small and therefore could not be expected to generate very large numbers of signatures. M. Kostovski further indicated plans to continue outreach to neighbouring and additional countries.
- d) European Society of Clinical Microbiology and Infectious Diseases – V. Fingerle reported that discussions with ESCMID leadership remained ongoing; R. Cánton additionally noted that recent leadership changes within ESCMID might have contributed to delays in responses and suggested further follow-up with society officers.
- e) College of American Pathologists (CAP) – A. Schuetz reported ongoing discussions with CAP, which was still internally evaluating how to handle such petition requests institutionally.
- f) Association of Public Health Laboratories (APHL) – S. Nguyen had previously established contact with K. Wroblewski at APHL, although no additional update was available and a response is still awaited.
- g) Swedish Society for Microbiology (SFM) – E.R.B. Moore reported that he had contacted the society, as well as an additional Swedish clinical microbiology society, and was awaiting responses.
- h) Infectious Diseases Society of America (IDSA) – follow-up activities assigned to K. Carroll remained pending, with no additional update provided during the meeting.
- i) SEIMC (Spain) – R. Cánton reported that the society had been contacted, although no response had yet been received.
- j) Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute (CLSI) – outreach activities coordinated by S. Copsey-Mawer remained ongoing, although no detailed update was provided during the meeting.
- k) Institute of Biomedical Science (IBMS) – activities coordinated by S. Copsey-Mawer remained ongoing.
- l) Society for Anaerobic Microbiology (SAM) – activities coordinated by S. Copsey-Mawer remained ongoing.
- m) American Society for Microbiology (ASM) – no update regarding dissemination of the petition through ASM was provided during the meeting.

Minute 8. Other reports from established tasks groups (regarding established CoMicProN targets)

a) ESCMID conference.

During the discussion on the ESCMID conference, V. Fingerle briefly reported on the CoMiCProN presentation presented at the meeting and noted that the presentation had been prepared collaboratively with substantial assistance from several committee members, particularly E.R.B. Moore and M. Göker, whom he explicitly thanked for their corrections and contributions. V. Fingerle stated that the presentation had been well received by attendees, with several participants approaching him afterwards for further discussion, including at least one individual from Switzerland who requested additional contact information. S. Butler-Wu was also mentioned as having attended the conference. V. Fingerle further commented on the possibility of organizing future ESCMID educational or “Meet the Expert” sessions devoted to bacterial nomenclature and taxonomy, although V. Fingerle noted that the ESCMID session selection process remained somewhat unclear and competitive. R. Cantón additionally commented on the complexity and opacity of ESCMID’s review and selection system for conference sessions, including the influence of study groups and thematic priorities.

b) Bruker.

M. Göker reported on the progress regarding a white paper on the use of prokaryotic names in Bruker's MALDI-TOF database. M. Göker noted that the only open question is at which online location the white paper will be placed. Once this is clarified, it can be linked to.

See Minute 4.13 concerning the issue of *Rhodococcus hoagii* in the Bruker database.

c) bioMérieux.

Regarding bioMérieux, no substantive update was provided during the meeting, as V. Collin was absent and had sent apologies.

d) NCBI

Regarding NCBI Taxonomy, E.R.B. Moore reported that he was still preparing a response concerning the lack of ICSP representation at the NCBI workshop during the ASM conference and intended to circulate the draft for comments before submission, emphasizing that the ICSP is also responsible for uncultivated taxa. G. Margos and V. Fingerle additionally reported ongoing communication with the NCBI Taxonomy team regarding implementation of the *Borrelia* subgenus, noting that although repeated assurances of a forthcoming response had been received, no substantive reply or implementation had yet occurred.

Minute 9. Brief reports on planned or submitted manuscripts

The committee briefly discussed the manuscript concerning the possible return of the subgenus category, with M. Göker noting that no substantial recent progress had been made because the matter was not currently considered highly urgent.

Minute 10. Brief reports on planned or submitted manuscripts

Follow-up discussions concerning LoRN.

a) Potential role of infrasubspecific categories, currently not formally regulated by the ICNP, and situation in plant pathology.

The committee discussed the possible role of infrasubspecific categories, currently not formally regulated by the ICNP, particularly in relation to plant pathology and the widespread use of pathovars. M. Göker presented a preliminary overview of existing below-subspecies designations such as pathovars, serovars, biovars, and genomovars, and raised the possibility of introducing a more general “variety” category within the ICNP framework that could encompass such classifications. Members discussed the practical and taxonomic implications of these categories in clinical microbiology and plant pathology, including their relationship to genomic classification, ecology, pathogenicity, and strain typing. Several participants emphasized the importance of nomenclatural standardization and stable reference systems, while also noting that any such category would likely remain optional and primarily serve fields already using detailed infrasubspecific classifications. No formal decision was attempted, but the vast majority of the participants agreed that the topic warranted further discussion and consultation with relevant experts, particularly from plant pathology.

b) Issue of *Mycobacterium bovis* vs. *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*.

The issue of *Mycobacterium bovis* versus *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* was only briefly mentioned during the broader discussion on infra-subspecific categories, with M. Göker noting that earlier discussions on whether subspecies-level differentiation was sufficient had partly motivated consideration of additional below-species classifications.

c) Other aspects of LoRN in the light of previous unfinished discussions.

The committee briefly revisited broader issues surrounding nomenclatural stability, taxonomy, and implementation of recommended names in databases and diagnostic contexts. The discussion was largely integrated into related topics concerning the online petition, database usage, plant pathogens, infra-subspecific categories, and communication with external organizations and database curators, without a separate formal conclusion or decision being reached under this agenda item.

Minute 11. Any other business

No additional committee business was raised.

Matters Arising / Action points

1. All committee members to continue updating and augmenting the CoMiCProN list of potential multipliers (start: 2025-08-05).
2. All committee members to confirm their attendance at the June ASM meeting in Washington, D.C., and coordinate logistics with E.R.B. Moore (start: 2026-01-13).
3. All committee members to assess and contribute, where possible, to the IJSEM manuscript on the return of the subgenus, to be revisited at a future meeting (start: 2026-02-10).
4. S. Butler-Wu to continue efforts to identify the appropriate contact person for risk group classification in the USA (start: 2024-04-02).
5. V. Collin to liaise with M. Göker regarding the usage of LoRN by bioMérieux (start: 2025-09-02).

6. S. Copsey-Mawer to follow up with NCTC contacts regarding potential CoMiCProN membership candidates (start: 2025-12-02).
7. M. Göker to process information from plant pathologists, once ready, and report updates (start: 2025-05-05).
8. G. Margos to proceed with targeted communication with PubMLST database curators, following further clarification of approach (start: 2026-05-05).
9. E.R.B. Moore to update the CoMiCProN details on the ICSP website, including the Zenodo link for meeting minutes (start: 2025-12-02).
10. E.R.B. Moore to prepare and circulate a draft response to NCBI regarding ICSP representation at the workshop (start: 2026-04-07).
11. J. Vázquez-Boland to initiate contact with EMBL/ENA to arrange a meeting on prokaryotic nomenclature (start: 2025-10-21).
12. J. Vázquez-Boland to follow up on the *Rhodococcus hoagii* issue in the Bruker database with relevant stakeholders (start: 2026-02-10).
13. M. Kostovski or M. Göker to upload the minutes of the April meeting to Zenodo (start: 2026-05-05).
14. V. Fingerle to continue follow-up communication with European Society of Clinical Microbiology and Infectious Diseases (ESCMID) leadership regarding dissemination of the online petition (start: 2026-02-23).
15. A. Schuetz to continue discussions with the College of American Pathologists (CAP) regarding dissemination of the online petition (start: 2026-02-23).
16. S. Nguyen to continue follow-up communication with the Association of Public Health Laboratories (APHL) regarding dissemination of the online petition (start: 2026-02-23).
17. E.R.B. Moore to continue follow-up communication with the Swedish Society for Microbiology (SFM) and related Swedish clinical microbiology organizations regarding dissemination of the online petition (start: 2026-02-23).
18. Karen Carroll to continue follow-up communication with the Infectious Diseases Society of America (IDSA) regarding dissemination of the online petition (start: 2026-02-23).
19. Rafael Cánton to continue follow-up communication with SEIMC regarding dissemination of the online petition (start: 2026-02-23).
- 20.
21. Sarah Copsey-Mawer to continue outreach activities with the Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute (CLSI), Institute of Biomedical Science (IBMS), and Society for Anaerobic Microbiology (SAM) regarding dissemination of the online petition (start: 2026-02-23).
- 22.
23. All members of the American Society for Microbiology (ASM) to continue efforts regarding possible dissemination of the online petition through ASM channels (start: 2026-02-23).